

GREEN SOUL

GreenSoul

Persuasive Eco-awareness for User Engagement through Networked Data Services

The GreenSoul project main objective is to achieve higher energy efficiency in public buildings by altering the way people use energy consuming shared devices (lights, printers) and personal devices (personal pluggable appliances). In order to achieve this goal, GreenSoul will apply a two-fold strategy:

- It will persuade users to increase their energy-awareness and change their e-consumption habits through a variety of techniques, from persuasive social applications to physical interaction mechanisms linked to the networked devices
- It will embed intelligence into the networked devices to allow them autonomously decide about their operational mode for energy efficiency purposes. GreenSouled devices will learn from users habits, acting only when wasteful energy behavior is detected or users do not heed device suggestions

Key Components

ENERGY SENSING

MANAGEMENT API

ENERGY MONITORING SYSTEM

SELF CONFIGURATION

PERSUASIVE INTERACTION

FEEDBACK

GREENSOULED-THING

BEHAVIOR MODELING

GOAL ESTABLISHMENT

COACHING

LINKED DATA LAYER

SOCIAL MEDIA INTERACTION

SOCIAL MEDIA

GreenSoul addresses objective EE-11-2015: **“New ICT-based solutions for energy efficiency”** of the Energy Efficient Buildings call of the H2020 work programme. In this topic, GreenSoul will contribute to the following impacts listed in the work programme:

- Systemic energy consumption and production and emissions reduction between **15%** and **30%**
- Fast deployment of innovative ICT solutions for energy efficiency
- Greater consumer understanding and engagement in energy efficiency
- Social media as multiplier hubs – GreenSoul will be linked to social platforms allows using them as dissemination channels for ICT solutions.

6. Intelligent control at device level (+5%)
5. Manual control due to behaviour change (+4%)
4. Awareness through EcoSoul platform (+3%)
3. Energy awareness spread to personnel (+4%)
2. Awareness of building energy manager (+2%)
1. Smart monitoring (+2%)

Partners

